

Study of Hematological Profile in Cases of Puberty Menorrhagia**Bulbul¹, RubyKumari², Puja Mahaseth³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Puberty Menorrhagia is a common gynecological disorder among adolescent girls. Puberty menorrhagia when accompanied by anemia and hypoproteinemia poses substantial difficulties among gynecologists to manage. Aims of this study is to find out the haematological status in cases of puberty menorrhagia, evaluate the frequency of haematological disorder in these cases and determine the relative frequency of different haematological disorder.

Methods: This observational cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar from March 2022 to February 2023.

Adolescent girls of age group 11 – 19 years attending Gynaecology OPD or Emergency with excessive Menstrual bleeding who conform to the Inclusion criteria were recruited for the study.

Results: The patients under study were adolescent girls of age group 11 – 19 years. The majority of patients (80%) were Between 11 – 15 years and belonged mainly to rural area (50%) and low socio-economic status (50%). Most of the girls (52%) had menarche between 10 – 12 years of age and 70% of Adolescent girls had complaints of menorrhagia with duration of symptomatology of less than 6 months (70%). The cases (84%) had moderate degree of anemia with symptom like weakness, Anorexia, palpitation along with menorrhagia. 6% of cases had low platelet count (<1 lakh) of which all 6% cases were diagnosed as Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura.

Conclusion: Reassurance, counselling of adolescent girls about reproductive physiology, regular follow-up balanced diet and long-term iron therapy go a long way in treatment of puberty menorrhagia.

Keywords: Gynecological complications, Thrombocytopenic purpura, Symptomatology.

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Introduction

Menarche is a hallmark event in the life of adolescent's girls. It marks the transition from childhood to puberty. Although mechanism triggering puberty and menarche remain uncertain, they are dependent on different factor eg. Genetics, nutrition, body weight and maturation of hypothalamic pituitary ovarian axis. The complete maturation of axis may take up to 2 years [1]. During this time it is common for Adolescent girls to present with menstrual irregularities. Puberty is defined as the period during which secondary sex characters begins to develop and the capability of sexual reproduction is attained. Puberty Menorrhagia is defined as excessive bleeding in amount (>80ml) or in duration (>7 days) between Menarche and 19 years of age [1]. Almost a quarter of population in developing countries comprises girls below 20 years [2]. In India, children under 15 years of age constitute about

40% of population [3]. Menstrual disorders affect 75% of adolescent females and are a leading reason for visit to physicians [4]. Post menarche cycles initially are often anovulatory. Without ovulation estrogenic effect is unopposed by endogenous progesterone, resulting in endometrial proliferation, with eventual excessive menstrual bleeding. However, in most of cases the reason is physiological but other associated pathological factors may also be common. These causes are hormonal in cases of anovulatory cycle. Haematological disorders that may be inherited or acquired [6]. Inherited disorders include Von willebrand's disease, Glanzmann's Thrombosthenia, Bernard Soulier's syndrome. Acquired includes Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura, Acute leukaemia, Bone marrow hypoplasia, Hepatic failure and drugs like warfarin. Other systemic diseases like polycystic ovarian

disease, hypothyroidism, and tuberculosis are also important causes of puberty menorrhagia. In all case of puberty menorrhagia, it is mandatory to exclude pregnancy especially an incomplete abortion or ectopic pregnancy. In persistent abnormal bleeding coagulation disorders and leukaemia should be ruled out. Occasionally menorrhagia is the only presenting symptom in a patient of coagulation disorder. In general prognosis is better when dysfunctional uterine bleeding starts after a period of regular menstruation than when it starts at menarche [7].

Aims and Objectives

The gynaecological problems of teenagers can pose difficulties in management not just from physical problem but also from associated emotional and psychological factors.

The young girl who has just started menstruating may find that she experiences excess menstrual loss both in amount and duration. This may be frightening not only for her but also for her family. The cause may be anovulation, endocrinological or haematological disorder. The present study aims to analyse cases of puberty menorrhagia at a multidisciplinary tertiary institute in terms of haematological profile.

Any adolescent with abnormal bleeding should undergo pregnancy test for exclusion of pregnancy mishap. The occurrence of heavy menses should prompt an evaluation of haematological status to rule out haematological disorder.

Laboratory evaluation should include Complete blood count, platelet count, bleeding time, clotting time, prothombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, platelet function tests.

Specific Objectives of Study:

1. Find out the haematological status in cases of puberty menorrhagia.
2. To evaluate the frequency of haematological disorder in these cases.
3. To determine the relative frequency of different haematological disorder.

Materials and Methods

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Bihar from March 2022 to February 2023. Adolescent girls of age group 11 – 19 years attending Gynaecology OPD or Emergency with excessive Menstrual bleeding who conform to the Inclusion criteria were recruited for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age group – 11 – 19 years
2. Menstrual abnormalities like menorrhagia, polymenorrhoea.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnancy.
2. Organic lesion, like fibroid, ovarian cyst, PID, Endometriosis.

Informed consent: Only those cases are recruited who gave written and informed consent.

Parameters of study

1. Complete haemogram.
2. Platelet count
3. Bleeding time, clotting time
4. Prothrombin time, APTT
5. Platelet function test (In selected cases)

Study Tool: Includes facilities for detailed haematological investigation in department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, DMCH, Laheriasarai, Bihar.

Study Technique: Patients were recruited from gynaecology OPD and emergency that fulfilled inclusion criteria and exempted from Inclusion criteria. After detailed History taking and clinical examination, cases subjected had been done after analysis of report.

Analysis of Data: Data so collected has been analysed using standard statically protocol like Median, Mean, and Standard deviation, P value.

Results and Analysis

50 patients with H/O abnormal uterine bleeding of age group of 11 – 19 years were studied in DMCH during March 2022 to February 2023. The result of this study is analysed below.

Table 1: Age distribution of 50 patients under study

Sl. No.	Age group (years)	No. of cases	%
1	11 - 13	20	40%
2	13 – 15	20	40%
3	15 – 17	5	10%
4	17 – 19	5	10%
	Total	50	100%

Study shows majority of the 50 patient (80%) were in the age group of 11 – 15 years.

Table 2: Socio –economic status according to family income

Socio-economic status (Income in Rs/month)	No. of cases	% of cases
Poor(< 1500)	10	20%
Low (1500- 5000)	25	50%
Middle (5000 – 10000)	10	20%
High (>10, 000)	5	10%

Majority of the patients belong to the poor to low socio-economic status which was commensurate with the patient attend our hospital.

Table 3: Education level

Class	No. of cases	% of cases
Illiterate	3	6%
Upto 4 th Standard	10	20%
5 th to 10 th standard	35	70%
>10 th	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Most of the patients were in 5th to 10th standard group.

Table 4: Geographical distribution of 50 patients

	No. of cases	%
Urban	15	30%
Rural	25	50%
Sub Urban	10	20%
Total	50	100%

Study shows menorrhagia was common in rural population.

Table 5: Age of Menarche

Age of Menarche	No. of cases	% of cases
< 12 years	26	52%
12 – 14 years	22	44%
> 14 years	02	4%

Table 5. shows most of the girls had menarche between 10 – 12 years of age.

Table 6: Duration of Symptomatology

Duration	No. of cases	%
Less than 6 months	35	70%
6 months – 1 year	10	20%
> 1 year	5	10%

As shown in table 6 almost 70% of patient had onset of menorrhagia since less than 6 months.

Table 7: Bleeding Pattern of 50 patients under study

Bleeding Pattern	No. of cases	%
Menorrhagia	36	72%
Poly menorrhagia	14	28%
Total	50	100%

Table 7 shows that Menorrhagia form the largest group 72%.

Table 8: Associated symptom among 50 patients under study

Associated symptoms	No. of cases	%
1) Dysmenorrhoea	2	4%
2) Abnormal white discharge	1	2%
3) Weakness, Anorexia, Palpitation	45	90%
4) Loss of weight, fever	2	4%
5) Weight gain	4	8%
6) Hirsutism	1	2%

Most common associated symptoms were weakness anorexia, palpitation that were 90%.

Table 9: Haemoglobin level at the time of First Visit

Hb gm %	No. of cases	%
> 10	1	2%
7 - 10	42	84%
4 – 6.9	7	14%
< 4	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Table 9 showed haemoglobin level at the time of their first visit. Most of the girls had moderate degree of anaemia 84%.

Table 10: Platelet count of 50 patients under study

Platelet Count / mm ³	No. of cases	%
< 50,000	1	2%
50,000 - < 1 lakh	2	4%
1 lakh – 2 lakhs	8	16%
> 2 lakhs	39	78%
Total	50	100%

Table 10 shows maximum number of patients had platelet count more than 2 lakh (78%). 3 patients had low platelet count Out of which 1 had count less than 50,000/ mm³.

Table 11: Bleeding Time of 50 patients under study

Bleeding Time	No. of cases	%
Up to 3 min	33	66
> 3 - < 7 min	13	26
7 – 10 min	4	8

Table 11 shows 66% of patient had bleeding time less than 3 mins. While 8% of patients had prolonged bleeding time.

Table 12: Coagulation profile of 50 cases under study

Prothrombin Time	No. of cases	%
12 – 16 Sec	47	94%
> 16 sec	3	6%

Table shows 94% of cases had normal prothrombin time that is between 12 to 16 sec.

Table 13: Activated Partial Thromboplastin time of 50 cases under study

APTT Value (sec)	No. of cases	% of cases
24 – 28 sec	27	54%
28 – 32 sec	23	46%
Total	50	100%

Table 13 shows 100% of cases had normal APTT Value.

Table 14: Platelet function test of 50 cases

Platelet function test	No. of cases	%
Normal	43	86%
Abnormal	1	2%
Not done	6	12%

Table 14 showed platelet function test was normal in 86% of cases while 2% of cases showed abnormal results. In one case VWF activity decreased with absent of Ristocetin induced platelet agglutination. In 6 cases platelet function test was not performed as during baseline investigation like USG, thyroid function test. They are diagnosed as PCOS, hypothyroidism and they responded well to treatment.

Table 15: Ultrasonographical finding of 50 cases under study

USG finding	No. of cases	%
Uterus Normal size adnexa normal	46	92%
Ovaries shows multiple follicles	4	8%

Up to 92% of cases had normal USG finding.

Table 16: Thyroid function test of 50 cases under study

TSH, T ₃ , T ₄	No. of cases	%
Normal TSH, T ₃ , T ₄	46	92%
↑TSH, ↓T ₃ , T ₄	4	8%

Out of 50 cases 46 cases (92%) had normal TSH, T₃, T₄ Value while 4 cases were diagnosed as hypothyroid during follow up.

Table 17: Different Causes of Menorrhagia in 50 cases under study

Causes	No. of cases	%
Anovulation	37	74%
Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura	3	6%
Poly cystic ovarian disease	4	8%
Von willebrand's disease	1	2%
Genital Tuberculosis	1	2%
Hypothyroidism	4	8%
Total	50	100%

Table 17 shows anovulatory bleeding occurred in 37 cases (74%). Three patients of menorrhagia had a diagnosis of Idiopathic Thrombocytopenic purpura, 4 patients were diagnosed to have PCOS.

Table 18: Frequency of haematological disorder

Haematological disorder	No. of cases	%
Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura	3	6%
Von Willbrand's disease	1	2%

Table 18 shows out of 50 cases, 4 cases (8%) had haematological disorder out of which Idiopathic thrombocytopenia was most common. The relative frequency of haematological disorders were: idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura $3/4 \times 100 = 75\%$. Von Willebrand's disease $1/4 \times 100 = 25\%$.

Discussion

In this present study 50 cases who were presented with complaints of abnormal uterine bleeding like menorrhagia, polymenorrhoea between age 11 to 19 years in the gynecology OPD and emergency were studied. The distribution of age of 50 patients were 40% cases in 11 – 13 years group, 40% in 13 – 15 years and 20% in 15 – 19 years. So majority of cases (80%) were in age group of 11 – 15 years.

Among 50 cases, 70% had education level between 5th to 10th standard while 20% had up to 4th standard. 50% of cases belonged to rural area, 30% from Urban and 20% from Sub urban area. The study by J. Chowdhury, Chaudhuri S, Sarkar A, Biswas PK had rural patient incidence of 55% [8]. Average age of menarche is 12.5 years in India [9]. In this study 52% of patients had Menarche below 12 years and 44% had menarche between 12 to 14 years of age. In study by J. Chowdhury 40% of patient had menarche between 12 and 13 years and 35.5% had menarche after 13 years [8]. In the present study 70% of patients had duration of the disease for less than 6 months and 30% had symptomatology of more than 6 months while in study by Rao [1] 62% of patient had menstrual disorder of case less than 6 months duration and in study by J. Chowdhury [8] 56.9% of patient had duration of the disease for less than 6 months.

Most common bleeding pattern of patients in this study was menorrhagia (72%), 28% of patients also had complaint of polymenorrhoea. Other commonly found associated symptom with menorrhagia were weakness, palpitation, anorexia in 90% of patient. 4% patients had history of loss of weight, appetite and low-grade fever while 8% of patient had history of weight gain. Hirsutism was found in 2 cases (4%). Among 50 cases under study 84% had moderate degree of anemia, i.e Hb between 7 – 10 gm% while no patient had very severe anemia (Hb <4 gm%). In study by Rao [1] 33% of patients had haemoglobin less than 6gm%. In study by J. Chowdhury [8] 23.07% of patients had moderate degree of anemia. In present study 74% of cases of menorrhagia was found to be due to anovulation, A review of literature showed that during puberty,

Maturation of the hypothalamic pituitary –ovarian axis is characterized by an increase in the frequency and amplitude of pulsatile GnRH, which initiates and regulates secretion of pituitary Gonadotropins [10]. During the prepubertal years, LH is secreted primarily at night in the episodic fashion. With the progression to puberty, LH peaks increase in a pattern similar to that seen at night.

The timing of these LH pulses is crucial in establishing normal ovulatory cycles. Increases in basal LH as well as immature timing of pulses result in anovulatory cycles. These cycles are characterized by levels of LH and FSH secretion that are sufficient to induce follicular development and Oestrogen production but inadequate to induce follicular maturation and ovulation. Thus, unopposed oestrogen stimulates endometrial growth. This ultimately outgrows its blood supply and architectural support, resulting in partial breakdown and shedding in an irregular manner. In adolescent 95% of cases of anovulation are due to the immaturity of HPO axis [11] Chaudhuri et al [12] found 71% of their patients suffered from dysfunction uterine bleeding. In study by J. Chowdhury [8] 61.5% of the patients had anovulation. In study by Rao [1] 80% of patients had anovulatory bleeding. In study by Smith YR [13] 46% of cases were due to anovulation while in study by Kanbur [14] Incidence of anovulatory bleeding was 90%.

The occurrence of excessively heavy irregular menses should prompt an evaluation of haematological status to rule out blood dyscrasias. In the present study 8% had Blood dyscrasias manifesting as DUB. Claessens and Cowell [5] reported 19% of adolescent with menorrhagia requiring hospitalization had an underlying coagulation disorder. A more recent retrospective study by Falcone et al [15] in 1994 found that 4.9% of admission over a period of 10 years were secondary to coagulopathy. The study by Rao [1] showed 8.5% had Blood dyscrasias. In study by J. Chowdhury the incidence was 15.3%. A study by Kadir RA [16] including all age groups Patients the incidence of bleeding disorder with menorrhagia since menarche was 8.9%. In Dilley A, Drews C [17] study the incidence was 10.7%. In study by Phillip CS, Faiz A [18] 47% of women were found to have haemostatic abnormalities.

Laboratory evaluation, includes complete blood count, platelet count, prothrombin time, partial thromboplastin time, bleeding time, platelet func-

tion test in selective cases. The most common coagulation disorders were Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura and Von Willebrand's disease. Out of 50 patients 3 patients ($3/50 \times 100 = 6\%$) had platelet count below 1 lakhs. 3 cases (6%) were diagnosed as idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura. In study by J. Chowdhury [8], Thrombocytopenia was presence in 9.2% of cases, while in study by Rao [1] 5.7% of cases had Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura. In another study by Bevan JA, Maloney KW [19] 10.13% of adolescent girl with menorrhagia had thrombocytopenia.

Acute idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura is most commonly seen in young and is immunological thrombocytopenia, caused by immuno-complexes containing viral antigen that bind to the platelet, FC receptor, or by antibodies produced against viral antigen that cross react with platelets. It can be associated with Infectious mononucleosis, acute toxoplasmosis, CMV infection, viral hepatitis and HIV [20].

8% of cases had prolonged bleeding time that was seen in cases idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura and VWF disease.

Platelet function test showed 2% abnormal result. Another rare case of menorrhagia was Von Willebrand's disease was found during study. The relative frequency of disease was 2%. Von Willebrand's disease is a genetic condition characterized by reduction in the quantity (Type I or type III) or quality (type II) of Von Willebrand's factor, a protein required for normal blood clotting [20]. Menorrhagia is a common symptom of Von Willebrand's disease [21,10]. In study by Claessen E, Cowell CA [5] the incidence of VWD was 1% in United States.

In study of Dilley A, Drews C [17] the prevalence of VWF disease was 15.9% among white and 1.4% among black, menorrhagic patients. In study of Bevan JA, Maloney KW [19] out of 14 girls 2 had type I Von Willebrand's disease. In a study by Saxena R, Gupta M at AIIMS(22), different tests were performed included bleeding time, platelet count, PT, APTT, PF3 release with ADP at 0 and 20 min, total PF3 assay, aggregation studies with collagen, ADP, adrenaline, arachidonic acid and ristocetin. Von Willebrand's disease was the most frequently found coagulation disorder (11.9%) among girls with menorrhagia. In study by Mikhailis, Varadarajan R [23] the prevalence of VWF deficiency was 36% among adolescent patients of menorrhagia.

Polycystic ovarian disease can be infrequently associated with irregular heavy bleeding in 30% of cases, as reported by Gold Zeiher et al [25]. In present study 8% of cases had PCOS. In Rao [1] study 2.8% of the causes of Puberty menorrhagia were due to polycystic ovarian disease, while in J.

Chowdhury [8] study the incidence was 3.07%. Diagnosis was confirmed by altered day 2 LH and FSH ratio, features of hyperandrogenism and ultrasonography diagnosed polycystic ovaries [26]. Hypothyroidism can be associated with Puberty menorrhagia. The frequency of hypothyroidism in present study was 8%. The study by Rao [1] showed 5.7% of cases were due to hypothyroidism. The menorrhagia associated with hypothyroidism responds promptly to the thyroid replacements, often in doses insufficient to correct the other manifestation of the condition. This suggests that thyroxine does have direct effect on spiral arterioles and on haemostasis at menstruation [7].

Genital Tuberculosis as a cause of menorrhagia was found in 2% of cases under study. In Rao [1] study 5.7% of patients had Genital tuberculosis while in study by J. Chowdhury [8] prevalence was 1.5%. The incidence of genital TB is about 1% amongst the gynaecological patients [24] attending the OPD in developing countries. Menorrhagia or irregular bleeding in genital TB is probably due to Ovarian involvement, pelvic congestion or endometrial lesions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, individualizing every case, excluding pregnancy, timely hospitalization, thorough history, physical examination and base line work up are clinical in the management of every case. Reassurance, counselling of adolescent girls about reproductive physiology, regular follow-up, balanced diet and long-term iron therapy go a long way in treatment of puberty menorrhagia.

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